

Aspects of Silane Thermal Decomposition
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Abstract: Silicon deposition is central to monolithic device integration, yet the fundamental growth mechanism of silane thermal decomposition remains incompletely rationalized. Here, the ostensibly simple chemical transformation is revisited with the aim of constructing a coherent macroscopic model for silicon growth. A meta-analysis combining conventional thermal decomposition studies with industrial chemical vapor deposition data yields substantial insight into the governing mechanisms of heterogeneous silane decomposition. Silane thermal decomposition is approximated as a quasi-static chemical transformation. And a simple zero-dimensional thermodynamic model, grounded in silane dissociation and bond energetics, reproduces thin-film growth rates with remarkable accuracy. The available evidence further indicates an unexpected multiplicity of activation energies which are then tentatively mapped for Si{100}. The implications for industrial chemical vapor deposition are significant. The contrasts in activation energy between crystallographic facets govern selectivity, faceting, and the transition from conformal to non-conformal growth, while increasingly elaborate homogeneous gas-phase mechanisms appear largely redundant in zero-dimensional thin-film modeling.

Keywords

G01. Fundamentals of Nucleation and Crystal Growth, G02. Surfaces and Interfaces, G04. Thin Films and Epitaxial Growth, T02. Group IV semiconductors, J01. Growth Simulation and Practice

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1. INTRODUCTION

Silicon devices are the backbone of today's electronic revolution. The achievement rests on a broad foundation of skills, with materials science playing a central role in enabling monolithic device integration. Over the decades, the industry has developed exceptional know-how in deposition of silicon and its related alloys [1] [2]. The advances are underpinned by a broad chemical toolbox encompassing multiple technical disciplines [3].

Silane is routinely used for silicon deposition since the emergence of integrated electronics. And from the field's early developments onward, sustained efforts have progressively built the present understanding of materials and methods. Nevertheless, complex growth mechanisms force a reliance on pragmatic black box approaches and industrial design-of-experiments methodologies [4] [5] [6] [7] [8]. Considerable empirical knowledge has accumulated over the years but remains fragmented across literature. But an integrative understanding of silane thermal decomposition is currently lacking, hindering the rational development of silicon thin films. Accordingly, a coherent composite picture of the underlying growth mechanism remains absent. In retrospect, understanding appears limited when contrasted with the extensive achievements in device fabrication. Further investigation remains warranted.

Nowadays, undoped silicon plays only niche roles [9] [10] [11] [12] [13]. But there remains a need to cautiously delineate the fundamentals of the simplest system, i.e., silicon deposition via silane, as insights extend readily to other chemistries. The task is a necessity for contrasting correctly alternate chemical routes. This paper assembles several underreported aspects of silane thermal decomposition (TD) and silicon deposition from silane, with the aim of presenting a comprehensive and coherent model of silicon chemical vapor deposition (CVD). Central to the investigation is the assumption that both techniques share the same underlying chemistry.

For clarity, the investigation is structured into several subsections covering targeted topics: Comparing TD to CVD, Silane thermal decomposition, Thermal Si deposition via silane, Thermodynamics of Si CVD, Inert carrier gas, Contribution of CVD to TD, Contribution of TD to CVD, Contribution of thermodynamics, Alternate precursor routes. An integrative model is outlined in the discussion.

2 Comparing TD to CVD

Here, thermal Si deposition and Si CVD are equivalent, and CVD is used to denote Si CVD. A detailed description of experimental procedures and chemical kinetics schemes lies outside the scope of this work. Only the most salient features are summarized here.

The underlying chemical reaction mechanisms of TD and CVD are closely related, though several important differences deserve emphasis. TD studies concentrate on a gas-phase process, whereas CVD emphasizes the complementary solid-phase growth, Table 1.

TD has long served as a tool for probing chemical kinetics, particularly for determining macroscopic reaction orders and activation energies [14] [15]. And investigations of Silane thermal decomposition predate the development of epitaxial silicon [16].

Table 1: Comparing Thermal Decomposition to Chemical Vapor Deposition.

Technique	TD	CVD
Aim	Chemical Kinetics determination	High Volume Manufacturing
Investigated phase	Gas	Solid
Reactor setup	Static, shock tube	Continuous supply
Volume	Small	Large
Data sampling	Continuous (time-resolved)	Discrete (separate experiments)

Measurement	Total pressure	Center of wafer growth rate
Carrier gas	No	Yes
Boundary layer	No	Yes
Wall temperature	Isothermal	Mostly cold wall
Process	Isochoric	Isobaric
Thermodynamic exponent	1 – (E/RT)	– E/RT
Governing equation	$-\frac{dp_{\text{SiH}_4}}{dt} = Ae^{-E/RT} p_{\text{SiH}_4}$	GR = $Ae^{-E/RT} p_{\text{SiH}_4}$
Temperature (°C)	370-490	550-1200
Total Pressure (Torr)	1–450	Reduced pressure to atmospheric
Precursor partial pressure	Large	Small
Deposition on	Wall, gas phase nucleation	Substrate and surroundings
Film	Undetermined but poly or amorphous	Epi, Poly, amorphous

CVD GR trends are assembled from a series of discrete experiments at fixed ratios in a continuous-flow reactor. By contrast, TD experiments capture the continuous rate of reaction of an enclosed gas phase. Early TD studies monitor the time evolution of pressure over a finite interval, after which the experiment is deliberately terminated. Later investigations employ gas chromatography or mass spectrometry to identify species present in the gas phase. Finally, some experiments set up CVD reactors with mass spectrometry for gas phase investigations [17].

3 Silane thermal decomposition

Silane is very stable at room temperature but starts to degrade at temperatures above 380°C. Complete decomposition is achieved above 500°C [16]. Therefore, TD experiments are typically conducted at [370-490]°C, as slow reaction rates facilitate measurements. The inner wall of the TD reaction vessel is coated with amorphous or polycrystalline silicon before measurements, so that the decomposition proceeds in a somewhat controlled surface. X-ray analysis in Stockland’s early study reveals an amorphous coating [18].

When monitoring the pressure of an enclosed vessel, the pressure rise is an indicator of the chemical reaction progress. The loss of one SiH₄(g) gives two H₂(g), and (P₀ – P) gives the amount of SiH₄ lost, where P₀ is the starting pressure and P is the total pressure.

Silicon thermal decomposition is inherently heterogeneous. In CVD, homogeneous gas-phase reactions may also occur, but they are suppressed through dilution. By contrast, TD high concentrations lead investigators to lean toward gas-phase reaction kinetics mechanisms [16] [19] [20] [21]. TD experiments starting partial pressures are significantly larger than for typical epitaxial Si deposition.

The partial reaction order with respect to silane is consistently unimolecular, aside from a few outliers, Table 2 [16] [18] [19] [20] [22] [23] [24] [25] [26] [27]. Rounded Activation Energies E cluster around two values, 52 or 56 kcal/mol (217 or 234 kJ/mol), Figure 1. Most studies report one value or the other, yet the bimodal distribution receives little notice. Jasinski’s study tentatively addresses homogeneous thermal decomposition, Table 2 [27]. Yet Jasinski’s E is well aligned with previous works. Early investigators become also progressively aware of a possible experimental bias from what is now understood as a hydrogen termination of the surface.

Table 2: Activation Energy of Silane TD. GC Gas Chromatography, MS Mass Spectrometry, IR Infra-Red

Author	Year	Method	P (Torr)	T (°C)	n	E kcal/mol (kJ/mol)
Farrow	1974	Ion Beam + MS	10 ⁻⁵ -0.4	20-1200	1	17 (71)
White	1985	Static	60-400	367-430	1	51.1 (214)
Purnell	1966	Static + GC	5-150	388 & 430	1	51.2 (214)
Hogness	1936	Static	43-557	380-490	1	51.8 (217)
Stockland	1948	Static	70-450	375-492	1	51.9 (217)
Jasinski	1985	Static + IR Laser + GC	20	-	-	52±7 (218±29)
Newman	1979	Shock Tube	4000	762-911	1	52.7 (220)
Neudorfl	1980	Static	590	305-400	1	55 (230)
Purnell	1966	Static + GC	35-230	375-430	³ / ₂	55.9 (234)
Robertson	1984	Static - Stirred flow	4.3-50	371-471	0.2±0.2	56 (234)
Devyatikh	1965	Static	20.8-54.3	420-461	1	56.1 (235)

Another characteristic of Silane TD, shared by most crystallogen, is an induction period or incubation time, noticed at the onset of the experiment [16] [28]. The effect is also reported for CVD [29] [30]. Purnell attributes the incubation period to gas-phase reactions that compensate for the release of molecular hydrogen during silicon deposition [19]. As a result, the net pressure remains essentially constant during the initial phase of decomposition. During the incubation period, significant amounts of trisilane are observed, together with a partial reaction order of ³/₂ with respect to hydrogen.

Figure 1: Histogram of E(TD), rounded to the nearest integer, Table 1. A double distribution is apparent with clusters at 52 and 56 kcal/mol (218 and 234 kJ/mol).

A brief comparison with germane is also interesting for contrasting silane TD kinetics. Hogness reports a unique partial reaction order of $n = \frac{3}{2}$ for GeH₄(g) thermal decomposition [31]. The result agrees with Purnell's reports for hydrogen at the incubation time. Hogness unknowingly investigates digermane, and Purnell and Walsh are observing a disilane TD specific to the incubation period of silane TD. Germane TD typically exhibits two successive mechanisms. The activations energies are 42 kcal/mol (176 kJ/mol) at the tail end of the experiment, in other words, at low partial pressure and 50 kcal/mol (209 kJ/mol) at the beginning of the experiment, or high partial pressure [22] [32]. Partial reaction orders are 0 and 1 respectively.

4 Thermal Si deposition via silane

Early reactors are lab made, with manual handling of small wafer diameters. The operating pressure is atmospheric. A limited gas purity is remediated with high temperature processing. Modern reactors handle large substrates with tight pressure control ranging from atmospheric to reduced pressure. Despite technological leaps over several decades, reported kinetics are relatively stable across reactors as demonstrated by activation energy consistency, Figures 2 and 3 [33] [34].

Figure 2: Left, Joyce 's Si{110} GR vs. virtual partial pressure. The precursor is lab made with a 98.7% purity. Right, Arrhenius plot of Si GR via Silane, $p_{\text{SiH}_4} = 1$ Torr. GR reaches a plateau at high temperature (low $1000/T$) and $E = 37 \pm 1$ kcal/mol (155 ± 4 kJ/mol). Substrates are lab made $70 \times 60 \times 15$ mm³ bars. Thickness is determined by stacking fault width. The atmospheric reactor is vertical with a substrate aligned with the flow. Experiments are carried out in 1963. Both plots are redrawn.

Figure 3: Bryant's review of Si GR rate, $P = 1$ atm, 1979. The plot is redrawn and simplified for clarity. The legend gives the year of publication, E in kcal/mol, p_{SiH_4} in Torr and the carrier gas. The vertical axis separation reflects the controlled variation in silane partial pressure. Si substrate crystal orientation is not mentioned in the review. Si films with a partial pressure of 0.76 Torr or less, are confirmed polycrystalline. E is estimated from lowest two datapoints (dashed lines are eye guides). Trends with E less than 40 kcal/mol (167 kJ/mol) are eliminated (6 datasets). For clarity, GR plateau values are not shown. After elimination, activation energies appear relatively consistent, at 46 kcal/mol (192 kJ/mol) or less. Emmanuel's experiment gives 53 kcal/mol (222 kJ/mol). In view of the limited temperature range, each value is a coarse low estimate of the actual activation energy.

Silane is a reactive gas at typical CVD process temperature. Thus, process engineers run into the risk of ruining the inner reactor with detrimental dusting and a premature coating. Therefore, Silane is diluted with molecular hydrogen to a percent value or less, for gas phase nucleation containment, to maintain inner reactor cleanliness and control parameters uniformity across large silicon wafers. As a result, up to a pressure of 1 atm, homogeneous nucleation is not significant for most CVD experiments, and thermal decomposition is engaged after a molecule contacts the substrate [12] [35]. Silane thermal decomposition is inherently a heterogeneous process. Incidentally, molecular hydrogen adds the benefit of a reducing ambient, disabling oxidizing impurities.

Typically, precursor depletion profile in single wafer horizontal reactors is undetermined, [32]. Consistent sets of experiments are achieved, as long the horizontal precursor depletion profile is not impacted by experiment parameters. Outstanding thickness uniformities are achieved across large silicon wafers in modern reactors, thanks to adequate heat and flow distributions and a wafer rotation system. An incubation time for nucleation is also reported in CVD experiments, but the effect is usually neglected for epitaxial films [29].

Macroscopic kinetics are captured with a unidimensional GR perpendicular to Silicon substrate. For convenience, deposition kinetics are usually reported for center of wafer measurements. Plain chemical kinetics models are used for the GR correlation to partial pressure, Equation 1, where A is a pre-exponential factor, $p_{SiH_4}^o$ is an inlet partial pressure, E is the activation energy, R the ideal gas constant and T temperature [36]. Si GR is sublinear and $\frac{1}{2} \leq n \leq 1$ is a partial reaction order of the precursor [37] [38].

Si Growth Rate

$$GR = \frac{\text{Atomic flux}}{\text{Area}} \propto \partial L / \partial t \propto A e^{-\frac{E}{RT}} (p_{SiH_4}^o)^n \quad (1)$$

Si GR via silane kinetics is first determined by Joyce in 1963, Figure 2 [33]. And the GR vs. p_{SiH_4} plot shows a sublinear trend. But typical deposition parameter space is reported with a unimolecular reaction order [12] [39] [40]. A partial reaction order of $\frac{1}{2}$ is also reported on few occasions on later reports [36] [41]. Vazquez-Pufleau reports a reaction order of $\frac{3}{2}$ for nucleation of silicon [42].

GR exhibits an Arrhenius-type temperature dependence as well, with a high temperature, or low $1/T$, GR plateau. Later investigations are in agreement, but confusion reigns over the actual activation energy, Figure 3 [6] [34] [40] [43].

There is also a very unusual trend of 3 consecutive sublinear segments reported by Chiang, Figure 4 [44]. Silane partial reaction order alternates between 1 and 0. Unfortunately, no activation energy is reported. Beer's Arrhenius plot featuring a double Activation Energy is in good agreement with Chiang's findings, Figure 5, [45]. Both Chiang's and Beer's reports have gone largely unnoticed. Lastly, a recent meta-analysis confined to $E > 40$ kcal/mol (167 kJ/mol) suggests the occurrence of at least 3 activation energies, Figure 6 [34] [43] [46] [47] [48] [49] [50] [51] [52] [53] [54] [55] [56] [57] [58] [59] [60] [61] [62] [63] [64] [65] [66] [67] [68] [69] [70] [71] [72] [73] [74] [75]. Regarding molecular hydrogen, several investigations consistently assign a non-zero partial reaction order to the molecular hydrogen carrier gas, together with an associated apparent activation energy [12] [37] [40] [76] [77] [78].

Figure 4: Chiang's Si GR via silane with He as carrier gas, 1971. $T = 910^{\circ}\text{C}$. The plot is redrawn and simplified for clarity. Three sharp increases in GR are noticed. Silane partial reaction order is alternatively 1 and nearly 0. Chiang assigns the staircase profile to interactions between hydrodynamics, thermodynamics and chemical kinetics consideration of the reactor system. The original report suggests all layers are single crystal with varying degrees of defect density. No activation energy is reported but TD investigations set the expectation to similar values. Thickness is determined by weight change. Reactor is a horizontal quartz tube with 1-inch substrates aligned with the flow.

Figure 5: Beer and Bloem's simplified Arrhenius plot, 1982, Sketch redrawn for clarity. $2.3 \text{ Torr} < p_{\text{SiH}_4} < 17.5 \text{ Torr}$. Growth kinetics of amorphous silicon layers are investigated. And the sampling might have included polycrystalline layers as well. Nevertheless, activation energies agree with most reports.

Figure 6: Meta-analysis of Si GR $E(\text{CVD})$, shown as a histogram. $E(\text{CVD})$ is clustering around 3 values, namely, 46.5, 49.5 and 54.5 kcal/mol (195, 207 and 228 kJ/mol). The enabling factor is not clearly determined. The plot is built out of 35 reports and 49 values. The precursor breakdown is the following: SiH_4 59%, SiH_3Cl 2%, SiH_2Cl_2 27%, SiCl_4 2%, Si_2Cl_6 4%, not disclosed 6%. Reported film crystallinity: single crystal 71%, Polysilicon 10%, amorphous Si 14%, not disclosed 4%. Time span: 1964-2021.

5 Thermodynamics of Si deposition

Thermodynamics is largely irrelevant to chemical kinetics experiments conducted under static conditions. The time evolution of pressure places the system without ambiguity in the domain of chemical kinetics. By contrast, Sedgwick has once advocated the application of thermodynamics to CVD, [79]. But the approach is by now considered ineffective [80]. However, early studies are invalidated by the inclusion of an unphysical reversible dissociative adsorption of $H_2(g)$ [81] [82] [83]. Recent investigations have shown that incorporating bond dissociation energy (BDE) restores the quantitative relevance of thermodynamics to CVD modeling [36] [84]. Table 3 summarizes the chemical-system approximations.

Table 3: Thermodynamic approximations for Si deposition

Center of wafer = 0D system
$SiH_4(g)$ precursor
No gas phase reactions
Exclusion of carrier gas
Fast kinetics with chemical equilibrium
Substitution of center of wafer p_{SiH_4} by $p_{SiH_4}^o$
Fixed depletion profile
$GR \propto$ supersaturation
$\Delta H \approx$ fractional BDE
$\Delta S = \Delta S(SiH_4, g)$
ΔH and ΔS transferable constants

The absence of molecular hydrogen dissociation on silicon surfaces is also well established [82] [84]. Molecular hydrogen desorption is effectively irreversible. Consequently, the carrier gas contribution to chemical equilibrium is excluded from the hydrogen conservation equations in this work.

The thermodynamic model for elemental deposition is simple in concept and leads, through direct algebraic development, to Equations (2)-(10). The dual-regime behavior of CVD is reproduced, and the growth rate is found to depend on both the reactant partial pressure and one-half of the reaction enthalpy. Once the modeling is completed, tedious algebra exercises enable mapping of the chemical system responses, Figure 7.

Chemical reaction

Dalton's Law of Partial Pressure

$$p_i^o = \frac{\phi_i^o}{\phi_{H_2}^o + \phi_{SiH_4}^o} \cdot P$$

Equilibrium partial pressure of molecular hydrogen

$$p_{H_2}^{eq} = 2(p_{SiH_4}^o - p_{SiH_4}^{eq}) \quad (3)$$

Equilibrium constant in term of partial pressures

$$K = \frac{(p_{H_2}^{eq})^2}{p_{SiH_4}^{eq}} = e^{-\frac{\Delta G}{RT}} \quad (4)$$

Quadratic equation

$$(p_{SiH_4}^{eq})^2 - (2p_{SiH_4}^o + K/4)p_{SiH_4}^{eq} + (p_{SiH_4}^o)^2 = 0 \quad (5)$$

Discriminant

$$\Delta = (2p_{SiH_4}^o + K/4)^2 - 4(p_{SiH_4}^o)^2 \quad (6)$$

First root

$$p_{SiH_4}^{eq} = 1/2 (2p_{SiH_4}^o + K/4 - \sqrt{\Delta}) \quad (7)$$

Growth Rate

$$GR = \frac{Atomic\ flux}{Area} = A \frac{M}{d\pi r^2} (p_{SiH_4}^o - p_{Si}^{eq}) \quad (8)$$

Low temperature limit

$$GR \approx A e^{\frac{\Delta S}{2R}} \frac{M}{d\pi r^2} e^{-\frac{\Delta H}{2RT}} (p_{GeH_4}^o)^{1/2} \quad (9)$$

High Temperature limit

$$GR \approx A \frac{M}{d\pi r^2} p_{GeH_4}^o \quad (10)$$

Figure 7. Left: Calculated GR as a function of silane partial pressure, at fixed temperature. Right: Corresponding calculated Arrhenius plot. The two plots are coupled by a straightforward mathematical transformation. The governing Gibbs energy is $\Delta G = (2 \times 50) - 0.0655 \times T$ kcal/mol, where ΔH is estimated from the experimental activation energy and ΔS corresponds to the entropy formation of silane at 650 °C. Both plots provide a faithful representation of silicon growth kinetics. Similar plots are obtained with any enthalpy of reaction. Partial reaction orders are well reproduced. Depending on the initial silane partial pressure, deposition onset occurs between 350°C and 420°C, in excellent agreement with experimental observations [37]. A log-log plot of GR vs. p_{SiH_4} indicates an apparent partial reaction order of $1/2$ across the full range. However, the experiments do not provide sufficient resolution to distinguish between reaction orders of 1 and $1/2$ at low flow rates, or between $1/2$ and 0 at high flow rates.

6 Inert carrier gas

Substantial increases in reaction rate are observed when hydrogen is replaced with an inert gas, Figures 8 and 9 [19] [41] [85] [86]. Activation energies for polysilicon are broadly consistent with expectations, Table 4 [41]. Meunier-Beillard's activation energies for epitaxial Si via silane are 44 kcal/mol (184 kJ/mol) at 40 Torr and 41 kcal/mol (172 kJ/mol) at 80 Torr [86] for nitrogen as opposed to 48 cal/mol (201 kJ/mol) for hydrogen [86].

To begin with, an inert carrier gas has no intrinsic influence on the reaction progress of an isobaric process such as in CVD. Thus, the response to dilution is consistent with a shift in the chemical equilibrium, as anticipated from the application of Le Chatelier's principle to molecular hydrogen contribution. The underlying implication is the carrier gas is in equilibrium with the surface. But the interpretation is at odds with the known chemistry of molecular hydrogen. There is no dissociative adsorption of molecular hydrogen. And each phase chemical potential cannot equalize, because of an unidentified barrier to dissociation [82]. Thus, alternate interpretations must be developed. TD experiments demonstrate the effect is not directly related to a boundary layer or flow dynamics, Figure 8.

Figure 8: Effect of added SF₆ on initial rate of silane TD at 430°C, 1966. Purnell's experiments are redrawn for clarity. The reaction rate is shifted up by adding SF₆.

Figure 9: Left: Si GR (R in Claassen's notation) at 700°C for different hydrogen-nitrogen mixtures, Claassen and Bloem, 1981, Redrawn for clarity. GR is altered by mixing an inert gas with reactant. Right: Same dataset replotted on a semi log scale. A linear trend is apparent when using the semi-log scale.

Table 4: Claassen’s activation energy of polysilicon via silane in hydrogen and nitrogen, from a Hot Wall Epitaxy reactor, 1982. Total pressure is 0.525 Torr. Polysilicon growth in nitrogen is aligned with Beer’s amorphous Si kinetics, Figure 5. But Claassen’s polysilicon growth in hydrogen appears anomalous.

p_{SiH_4} (Pa)	$\text{H}_2(\text{g})$ kcal/mol (kJ/mol)	$\text{N}_2(\text{g})$ kcal/mol (kJ/mol)
0.21	-	49.4 (207)
0.41	36.4 (152)	-
0.51	-	48.0 (201)
0.82	38.5 (161)	-
3.3	42.5 (178)	-
19.0	39.0 (163)	37.3 (156)

Most kinetic schemes begin with the thermal activation of the precursor during the initiation stage. This process is generally attributed to collisions with a third-body partner, as represented in Equation (10). In other words, the GR increase is consistent with an energy-transfer effect influencing the effective precursor sticking coefficient [87]. The dependence on energy transfer is consistent with the mass-transfer-limited regime commonly attributed to CVD [4] [32] [76] [88].

Third-body collision

7 Contribution of CVD to TD

Silane TD is acknowledged as a heterogeneous process. Thus, the chemical reaction takes place on the surface, namely the reaction vessel walls. And CVD benefits from the effect for the deposition of a thin film on silicon substrates and reactor surroundings. In other words, solid growth is the limiting step in the chemical mechanism.

The perception of the GR evolution gives an inside view of TD. Growth rate trends are sublinear. And silane partial reaction order typically follows a successive sequence. First a unimolecular order, next a transition from 1 to $\frac{1}{2}$, then $n = \frac{1}{2}$ dominates, before reaching lastly a GR plateau, Figure 7 [38].

The insight is critical for an understanding of the GR sampled by TD. Most TD experiments report a unimolecular reaction order. Thus, TD experiments appear sampling the mass-transfer regime of the two-regime model of CVD, when using Deal-Grove model terminology [89].

Incidentally, the two-regime model collapses for TD. The boundary layer is not a controlling parameter in a static system as there is no flow. And the mass transfer regime ($n = 1$) is also controlled by temperature since an activation energy is attached to the unimolecular reaction order. In other words, the system is both under kinetic control and mass transfer control when pushing the two-regime model to the limit [89].

A couple of values of $E(\text{CVD})$ are not reported in TD, $E(\text{CVD}) = 46.5$ kcal/mol (195 kJ/mol), and $E(\text{CVD}) = 38$ kcal/mol (159 kJ/mol), Figure 3 and 5 [34] [45]. Beer and Bloem’s findings indicate the unreported E are found only at higher temperature, outside the typical investigation range of TD experiments.

A review of TD investigation shows also a few outliers. Robertson’s $n = 0.2 \pm 0.2$ is notable. The result takes all its meaning with the realization Robertson’s experiment is sampling the GR parameter space with a variable partial reaction order of $\frac{1}{2} < n < 0$. And Jasinsky’s parameter space characterized by $E = 52 \pm 7$ kcal/mol (218 \pm 29 kJ/mol) must have sampled all 3 main activation energies.

8 Contribution of TD to CVD.

TD and CVD activations energies are comparable. In short, $E(\text{CVD}) \approx E(\text{TD})$. The immediate inference is the validation of $E(\text{CVD})$. $E(\text{TD})$ is immune to experimental biases plaguing horizontal continuous flow reactors. Incidentally, TD vindicates the center of wafer measurements practice for the determination of CVD growth kinetics.

Furthermore, CVD activation energies are not specific to a determined crystallinity. $E = 50$ kcal/mol (209 kJ/mol) and $E = 56$ kcal/mol (234 kJ/mol) appear both attached to epitactic, amorphous and polycrystalline Silicon.

Another largely underreported aspect of TD emerges. There are at least two mechanisms validated by TD. And GeH_4 TD hints of a coexistence [22] [32]. A small offset is noted for one: $E(\text{TD}) = 52$ kcal/mol (218 kJ/mol) as opposed to $E(\text{CVD}) = 50$ kcal/mol (209 kJ/mol). The source of the offset is still unclear.

Only one silane TD observation remains unaccounted for, namely Farrow's report of $E(\text{TD}) = 17$ kcal/mol (71 kJ/mol), Table 2. It can be noted in passing that $17 \times 3 = 51$. But there is no evidence of a determined integer ratio. A clear interpretation is lacking but the unusual activation energy is assigned to the specifics of Farrow's experimental set-up. As the finding is isolated, it may be safely disregarded at present.

9 Contribution of Thermodynamics

A rigorous application of thermodynamics to silane TD assigns the additive inverse of the enthalpy of formation of silane to the enthalpy of the thermal decomposition. To restate the obvious, experiments do not match expectations. Nevertheless, thermodynamics offers an alternative narrative to CVD two-regime model, [89]. The chemical reaction attains completion at the GR plateau. And a chemical equilibrium is reached before completion in the thermally controlled regime. Thermodynamics brings also into focus the effective value of energy activation as one half of the actual enthalpy of reaction at play in the chemical system. When activation energies are doubled, near coincidence with bond dissociation energy become apparent, Table 5.

Table 5: Identification of E to a fractional BDE, unit in kcal/mol (kJ/mol), [38] [90].

Activation Energie E	Technique	2×E	Bond	BDE
46 (192)	CVD	92 (385)	Si-H	91.7 (384)
50-52 (209-218)	CVD and TD	100-104 (418-435)	H-H	104.2 (436)
55 (230)	CVD and TD	110 (460)	Si-Si	105.2 (440)

The matching to Si-H is near perfect for $E = 46$ kcal/mol (192 kJ/mol). Comparison with Germane TD comforts the assignment as a matching to Ge-H is also observed, $E = 42$ kcal/mol (173 kJ/mol) as opposed to $\frac{1}{2}\text{BDE}(\text{Ge-H}) = 41.7$ kcal/mol (174 kJ/mol). There are two possible candidates for 50–52 kcal/mol (209-218 kJ/mol), namely H-H and Si-Si. The activation energy is shared by most p-block hydrides whose common factor is hydrogen, [38]. To date, there is no confirmed observation of molecular H_2 at the silicon surface. Nevertheless, the energy is assigned to $\text{BDE}(\text{H-H})$ as the matching to $E(\text{TD})$ is near perfect. A small offset between $E(\text{CVD}) = 50$ kcal/mol (209 kJ/mol) and $E(\text{TD}) = 52$ kcal/mol (218 kJ/mol) is also apparent. The remaining activation energy $E = 55$ kcal/mol (230 kJ/mol) is assigned to a Si-Si. Again, there is a noticeable small mismatch of a few kcal/mol between E and $\frac{1}{2}$ BDE(Si-Si). The discrepancy might be rooted in a strained bond.

Thermodynamics clarifies also the role of the total pressure P on the CVD reaction kinetics [12] [51] [65]. A fixed $p_{\text{SiH}_4}^0$, total pressure P does not directly affect the equilibrium composition, provided that (i) depletion profiles remain unchanged with pressure and (ii) all relevant gas flows are properly

accounted for in the calculation of partial pressures. At fixed $\text{SiH}_4(\text{g}) / \text{H}_2(\text{g})$ mole ratio, a change in total pressure effectively modulates the reactant partial pressures. As a result, trendlines analogous to those shown in Figure 7 are recovered after an appropriate substitution of the partial-pressure axis by total pressure.

Thermodynamics helps disentangle the contribution of molecular hydrogen as well. The rate of formation molecular hydrogen is twice that of solid silicon. In contrast, CVD experiments report for molecular hydrogen: $n(\text{H}_2) = -1, -\frac{1}{2},$ and 0 . The simultaneous observation of a unimolecular reaction order for silane and either -1 or $-\frac{1}{2}$ for $n(\text{H}_2)$ indeed obscures the underlying reaction mechanism.

Overall, $n(\text{H}_2)$ appears as the additive inverse of $n(\text{SiH}_4)$ [40] [77]. Experimental $n(\text{H}_2)$ is interpreted as an empirical correlation rather than evidence of causation, since the explored parameter space is dominated by mass-transport limited conditions [4] [32] [76] [88]. The apparent hydrogen dependence is more plausibly attributed to a bias rooted in an unaccounted controlled silane dilution than to an intrinsic chemical involvement of molecular hydrogen, Figure 10.

Figure 10: Simplified sketch of GR Arrhenius plot when adding hydrogen. Silane and molecular hydrogen partial reaction orders are overlaid for clarity. Controlled molecular hydrogen additions effectively dilute silane and as a result, silane partial pressure is reduced. The Arrhenius plot of the diluted experiment lays underneath the control experiment. Experiments assign then to molecular hydrogen the dilution effect. In the saturation regime, partial reaction orders are $+1$ for silane and -1 for molecular hydrogen and in the fall-off regime, $1/2$ and $-1/2$. Key to the interpretation is the shift to higher temperature of the fall-off section. When the diluted experiment crosses the knee, silane partial reaction order is 1 or less, and molecular hydrogen reaction order is $-1/2$ or less. A 0 partial reaction order is correct for well-designed experiments or when the variation range is too small.

10 Alternate precursor routes

The focus of this study is the clarification of the thermal decomposition of silane, but a brief comparison to chlorosilanes brings additional insights. Only a few datasets are directly relevant. Eversteyn compares silane with several chlorosilanes, but the experiments are dated and, unfortunately, substrate orientation is not disclosed [91]. At the time of publication, $\text{Si}\{111\}$ is the mainstream crystal orientation. The reported average activation energies are all similar, approximately 33 kcal/mol (138 kJ/mol) for SiH_4 , SiH_2Cl_2 , SiHCl_3 , and SiCl_4 [91]. A cursory inspection of the Arrhenius plots shows a neglected change of slope at low temperature. Tail end activation energies become 51 kcal/mol (213 kJ/mol) for SiCl_4 , and 45 kcal/mol (188 kJ/mol) for SiHCl_3 .

More recent data obtained using $\text{Si}\{100\}$ substrates appear in Meyer's review [72]. Finally, Tomasini publishes a related study including SiH_3Cl . Silane activation energy appears as 46.5 kcal/mol (195 kJ/mol) in both sets, in good agreement with previous epitaxial experiments, Figure 3 and Table 6 [70]. Chlorosilanes activation energies are consistent with TD findings, with E either 50 kcal/mol (209 kJ/mol) or 55 kcal/mol (230 kJ/mol). The change in chemistry does not significantly affect the energetic

fundamentals of the decomposition process. But relative GR are impacted as the added chlorine reduces the precursor efficiency. Thus, the fundamental solid growth mechanism is expected to be similar.

Table 6: Compared activation energies for several precursors. E and σ in kcal/mol (kJ/mol). Meyer's partial pressures are not documented. N is the sample size for the best fit. σ is a standard deviation, R^2 is a coefficient of determination.

Author	Precursor	p_{Si} (Pa)	E	σ	R^2	N
Meyer	SiH ₄	Not disclosed	46.5 (195)	0.6 (2.5)	0.99951	5
Meyer	SiH ₂ Cl ₂	Not disclosed	51.4 (215)	0.7 (2.9)	0.99892	8
Tomasini	SiH ₄	27	46.5 (195)	0.5 (2.1)	0.99964	5
Tomasini	SiH ₃ Cl	27	49 (205)	0.6 (2.5)	0.99971	4
Tomasini	SiH ₂ Cl ₂	27	55 (230)	0.7 (2.9)	0.99945	5

To the best knowledge of the author, no study has systematically compared film growth kinetics across different Si(hkl) orientations, when silane is used as the sole precursor. This gap is a notable shortcoming in the characterization of silane thermal decomposition. By contrast, several investigations using chlorinated silanes do report orientation-dependent behavior, and these studies offer partial guidance for anticipating how surface orientation might influence growth and faceting.

Mendelson's and later Tung's investigations with high temperature Si CVD via SiCl₄ fingerprint trends with a GR dip at Si{111} and about similar GR for Si{100} and Si{110} [38] [92] [93]. High temperature GR appear dominated by the areal atomic packing. Crystallographic planes with the highest areal density exhibit the lower GR.

In a recent study, Loubet provided a detailed characterization of GR on patterned wafer facets, from which activation energies were extracted for several {hkl} orientations, Table 7 [67] [94]. By contrast, Arrhenius plots for a few low index planes have also been determined, Table 7 [95]. Both investigations are using SiH₂Cl₂. And activation energies are aligned. Si{100} crystal growth appears in two different parameter spaces as for Loubet's E = 51.7 kcal/mol (216 kJ/mol) and for Hartmann's E = 57.2 kcal/mol (239 kJ/mol). Hartmann's Si{100} E reduces to 55.5 kcal/mol (232 kJ/mol) after exclusion of the experiment at the lowest temperature. The measurement is possibly an outlier. The final takeaway is activation energies are specific to each {hkl}.

Table 7: E vs Si{hkl} for blanket epi (Hartmann) and film faceting (Loubet). E in kcal/mol (kJ/mol). Hartman's Si{100} lowest temperature GR is excluded for the activation energy determination. † Corrected with a datapoint elimination.

Year	Author	Growth	Si{100}	Si{911}	Si{311}	Si{111}	Si{110}
2007	Loubet	Facet	51.7 (216)	43.4 (182)	42.6 (178)	59.8 (250)	-
2006	Hartmann	Blanket	55.5 (232)†	-	-	61.2 (256)	59.5 (249)

11 Discussion

In essence, TD experiments monitor the macroscopic evolution of gas volumes, and this evolution reflects the atomic structure of the reacting matter. So, TD follows the tradition of early 19th century investigations on the law of combining volumes, [96]. The distinguishing feature with silane is the participation of the solid, since the chemical process is fundamentally a heterogeneous chemical process, [4].

Reaction kinetics fingerprints an underlying atomic structure. Silane thermal decomposition is inferred as an elementary step, most likely the final incorporation of an adatom into the lattice.

Experiments capture a surface effect on which a gas phase composition has a limited influence as demonstrated by growth kinetics similarity between distinct chlorosilanes, including silane.

The situation makes elaborate homogeneous gas-phase reaction mechanisms somewhat unnecessary, at least for zero-dimensional thin-film modeling. Accordingly, computational fluid dynamics models can rely on simplified chemical-kinetics schemes whose primary role is to compute the partial-pressure distribution of the active precursor, chiefly silane, over large areas.

In retrospect, early emphasis on detailed chemical schemes, based on an immature understanding of thermal decomposition, has misdirected subsequent developments. Because the transformation is characterized by macroscopic parameters (P , GR), molecular-level insight remains limited. Consequently, this work does not attempt to determine a kinetic scheme. Instead, it aims to provide tentatively a comprehensive macroscopic description of the transformation, establishing a validated foundation for the future development of kinetic models.

At first glance, silane TD appears as a kinetically controlled system. But CVD is also remarkably responsive to thermodynamics. A pronounced incubation time is consistently observed. An inert gas effect is likewise evident. Si GR exhibits a strong crystallographic dependence, reflecting differences in areal atomic packing among crystal planes. Finally, chemical kinetics appear broadly similar across precursors once absolute growth rates are disregarded.

A simple macroscopic growth model reconciles TD and CVD main chemistry. At first contact, the solid surface is effectively isolated from the gas phase by an undefined barrier, but the precursor eventually permeates through, in proportion to its gas-phase concentration, Figure 11. This delay corresponds to the incubation time commonly observed in TD and CVD experiments. Chemisorbed silane is strongly coupled to gas phase silane, otherwise a gas-solid equilibrium hypothesis would fail in modeling the system. Thus, silane thermal decomposition fingerprints a quasi-static chemical transformation.

The available activation energies provide strong evidence for multiple decomposition pathways on Si{100}, Figure 12. A vertical section of the T vs. p_{SiH_4} plot leads to an Arrhenius plot after substitution of E with corresponding GR , and a T axis transformation to $1/T$. A horizontal section leads to Chiang's plot. Chiang's rise in GR fingerprints a sudden decrease in E . Appearances are E drops when either T is in the medium temperature range or higher silane partial pressure. The reported values span materials of differing crystallinities, although most are also documented specifically for Si{100}. Germane TD confirms T and p_{SiH_4} are the determining criteria. Similar behavior is likely to occur on other facets, but the current experimental data is insufficient to delineate respective domains.

Figure 11: Model of Silane TD. The crystal growth interface is somewhat isolated from the ambient silane gas. The unidentified barrier is hypothesized identical to the energy barrier disabling $H_2(g)$ adsorption. The barrier existence explains the lack of immediate collapse of the gas phase into a solid. The growth interface is still fed in precursor via the barrier. The barrier impedes immediate equalization of chemical potentials between the gas phase and the solid. As a result, the gas phase is not in equilibrium with the solid. Reactants are in equilibrium at the interface, once the nutrients have diffused throughout. The reduced dimensionality of the system may likewise account for the persistence of a $1/2$ reaction order in some odd-numbered p-block hydrides, with Stock's rate law for stibine serving as a representative case. Overall, macroscopic gas phase reaction stoichiometry is conserved, at least for silane.

The finding is particularly relevant for industrial CVD, where fundamental mechanisms remain poorly characterized. Process selectivity and facet formation are largely governed by differences in activation energy across crystallographic planes. At high temperature, growth tends to be conformal, whereas lower temperatures promote faceting [97]. Depending on the processing window, the activation-energy contrast between facets may be diminished or amplified, leading to different film morphology outcomes. Similar trends are expected in selective deposition processes as free-standing nucleation on a dielectric is oriented along {111} as opposed to lattice matched Si{100} on openings. The most favorable conditions for selectivity occur when the activation-energy difference between Si{100} and Si{111} is maximized.

Figure 12: Tentative (p_{SiH_4} , T) mapping the activation energy of silane thermal decomposition on Si{100}. Probable areas are tentatively assigned, based on fragmented results available. Activation energies of 46 and 38 kcal/mol (192 and 159 kJ/mol) have not yet been reported with TD. The assigned cause is as simple as TD experiments do not sample the parameter space of existence of the activation energies. Zone boundaries are currently not mapped. And the transition from 46/50 (192/209) to 38 kcal/mol (159 kJ/mol) might be gradual. The 38 kcal/mol (159 kJ/mol) domain might be rooted in a collapse of the fixed depletion profile assumption. Dislocation-assisted growth mechanisms enhance GR, but the lattice collapse is not impacting E significantly. Similar activation energies are expected for single crystal, dislocated and amorphous films. Similar maps are also anticipated for any crystal facets, but domain boundaries are shifted. Available evidence suggests non {100} facet might have additional activation energies in relation to their respective surface energies [98].

Thermodynamic control of the decomposition requires further explanation and remains the most challenging aspect to account for, especially for an accidental thermodynamicist. A gas phase in equilibrium with the surface leads to an enthalpy of reaction equal to the additive inverse of silane enthalpy of formation. But expectations are not supported by experiments. The issue resolution can be approached from several angles, not necessarily mutually exclusive.

Since interface reactant and products are no longer in the standard state, appropriate enthalpies of formation must be determined. Furthermore, E closely matches a fractional BDE. A pragmatic approach is to treat experimental activation energy as an estimate of the reaction enthalpy. The finding opens also several lines of investigation, either thin film GR are governed by the surface energy of the system, or the thermodynamic model has inadvertently uncovered the adsorption-isotherm relationship controlling GR [98].

The reduced dimensionality of the system might explain as well why some odd numbered p -block hydrides still exhibit a partial reaction order of $\frac{1}{2}$ as with Stock's rate law for stibine [15]. The activation energy gives an insight into the surface reconstruction via the type of bonds activated and the unit cell area. Different number of bonds for a fixed cell area give rise to harmonic series in activation energies.

12 Conclusion

Silane is a relatively simple molecule, nevertheless the hydride TD offers a challenging case study for standard chemical kinetics procedures. Conventional, narrowly scoped approaches have repeatedly failed to dispel the confusion currently prevailing. Conflicting activation energies, as well as conflicting partial reaction orders invite continued analysis beyond kinetic parameterization of the gas phase. A complete characterization of solid growth becomes a necessity. The hydride thermal decomposition provides an instructive case study for extending chemical kinetics analysis. Interpretation of TD kinetics necessitates a thorough understanding of the solid deposition. And TD investigations are critical for the validation of CVD kinetics.

Then a simple thermodynamic model demonstrates that a minimal treatment is sufficient to reproduce the familiar CVD two-regime model and GR partial reaction orders. Identification of the carrier gas irrelevance to the reaction pathway is fundamental to mechanism development. An interface barrier is also another critical concept, underlying the absence of instantaneous gas-to-solid conversion. The gas-phase chemical potential is not aligned with solid-phase chemical potential while local equilibrium at the isolated interface is preserved. Under these conditions, silane thermal decomposition of silane is approximated as a quasi-static chemical transformation. Accordingly, a collection of disparate findings is unified within a coherent theoretical framework.

The thermodynamic control of thermal decomposition remains the most challenging aspect to reconcile rigorously, especially when considering molecular hydrogen is not in equilibrium with the surface. But reactants and products at the interface depart from their standard states. And the present analysis already narrows the field. Silicon deposition is understood as bond-driven, enabling a compact framework for interpretation and optimization of Si deposition. Additional lines of inquiry become apparent, either GR is fundamentally governed by surface energies, or the work has inadvertently uncovered an effective adsorption-isotherm relationship controlling GR.

Silicon deposition exhibits several distinct activation energies. A tentative mapping of the Si{100} activation energies in the (T, p_{SiH_4}) space is proposed, although the current experimental record remains too limited for an accurate delineation of the boundaries between the various domains. Similar findings are expected for other crystallographic orientations, but data collection is excessively scarce. Furthermore, definitive determination of the activation energy of epitaxial silicon growth opens the way to reliable calibration and cross-calibration of industrial chemical reactors. This work incidentally demonstrates the value of a fine activation energy analysis for epitaxial process development.

While silane is the narrow focus of this investigation, similar findings are anticipated for any p-block material, crystal growth and in the field of heterogeneous catalysis.

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ABBREVIATIONS

0D	Zero-dimensional
A	Pre-exponential factor
AU	Arbitrary Units
BDE	Bond Dissociation Energy
CVD	Chemical Vapor Deposition
d	Density
E	Activation Energy
E(TD)	Thermal decomposition Activation Energy
E(CVD)	Chemical Vapor Deposition Activation Energy
GC	Gas Chromatography
H	Enthalpy of reaction
IR	Infrared
K	Equilibrium constant
M	Third body
\mathcal{M}	Molar Mass
MS	Mass Spectrometry
N	Sample size
n	Partial reaction order
n(H ₂)	Partial reaction order of H ₂ (g)
n(SiH ₄)	Partial reaction order of SiH ₄ (g)
P	Total pressure
p ^o	Inlet partial pressure
p _{Si}	Partial pressure of precursor SiH _{4-x} Cl _x
R	Growth Rate (Claassen)
R	Ideal gas constant
R ²	Coefficient of determination
S	Entropy of reaction
r	Radius
T	Temperature
TD	Thermal Decomposition
αSi	Amorphous Silicon
Δ	Discriminant
ΔG	Gibbs Energy
σ	Standard deviation
φ ^o	Inlet Volumetric flow

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